

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing

Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Development of Listenership for Indian Hindustani Music By Using Mimetic Comprehension

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August, 2019

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Acknowledgments

First of all, I would like to thank Angel Blanco, for being my supervisor and helping me with the direction of the thesis and getting me back on track whenever I was lost. Especially thanks to Xavier Serra, for accepting me as a masters student at MTG and for motivating me for the thesis.

I also want to express my gratitude to the entire group of people from the Music Technology Group, for helping me and inspiring me in every possible way.

And finally and most importantly, I would like to thank my parents and my brother for making this journey possible and for being there whenever I needed support.

The journey which I started with MTG helped me open up my mind to a new dimension of technology and music, and their interconnectedness. It has put me on a path which I am glad to follow.

Abstract

How can we train adults in listenership for Indian Hindustani music belonging to a different culture? Can mimetic comprehension of beat patterns using hand gestures and visual feedback improve rhythm perception and recognition ability?

Culture influences the processing of music rhythm, but the precise aspects are still unknown. We developed a rhythm training setup to perform a music cognitive study and investigate the effects of visual feedback enforced mimetic comprehension of Hindustani Rhythmic Beat Patterns (also called Talas) on participants with different musical cultural background. The participants were trained in three different Talas: Tintal (16 beats), Ektal (12 beats) and Jhaptal (10 Beats). We investigated whether the participants are able to (1) detect the “Sam”, which is the starting beat of every beat cycle by pressing the key “s” on keyboard while listening to the audio excerpt and (2) recognize the Tal in 12 different audio excerpts of Hindustani Classical Music. Participants in the experimental group were trained with videos comprising visual feedback through hand gestures which were asked to imitate by themselves, while the participants of the control group were trained without visual feedback of hand gestures and just listening passively to the Talas. Their performance was recorded to measure the improvement in rhythm comprehending ability.

Our results indicated that the training may be successful in developing listenership and appreciation for Indian Hindustani Music focusing more on its rhythm aspects. Also, we found out that participants in the experimental group were better at recognizing the beat pattern than the participants of the control group. However the sample size is still too small to draw conclusions from the results.

Keywords: Music Cognition, Music Teaching, Listenership, Mimetic Comprehension, Indian Music.

Chapter 1

Introduction & State of the Art

1.1 Music Enculturation

Music as we know is a perceptual and cognitive act of construction of conceptual understanding of its structure. Music listening is about pattern detection, identification, comparison, and evaluation. This is what Honing refers as musicality [1].

While listening to music, we try to find relation between tonal-rhythmic patterns [2]. But, development of comprehension, appreciation and understanding of a specific music style depends on enculturation, which is a temporary extended process that transforms our overall cognitive capacities [3]. Music is an embodied and encultured activity as all forms of musicing like performing, composing and conducting are examples of play across our memory, embodiment and situated consciousness. It also includes multisensory experiences and actions that lead to perception of sounds [4]. The cognitive processes of music enculturation takes place early on in life [5], during the phase of childhood, and not much research has been done on how adults are able to develop the comprehension skills of music outside their own culture.

There have been studies where East African and North American adults were tested on perception, production, and beat tapping for rhythms derived from East African and Western music to measure the influence of culture on rhythm processing [6]. To measure rhythm discrimination, participants identified if the pair of beats were same or different, for rhythm production, participants produced rhythms after listening to them and for beat tapping, participants tapped the beat along with rhythm. The results demonstrated that participants of both groups showed no variation for rhythm discrimination task, for rhythm production, participants belonging to East-Africa showed an affect of cultural familiarity, leading to significant interaction and for beat

tapping, participants of both groups tapped the beat more accurately for culturally familiar music. This shows that culture does influence processing of musical rhythm.

Also, music perception is not only influenced by enculturation or incidental exposure to music but also by music lessons and other forms of musical enrichment [7]. In some previous studies, American and Turkish listeners were asked to detect metrical changes in the context of simple meter and complex meter finding out that metrical sensitivity was being modulated by both culture and musical training [8]. In their results trained musicians were found generally to be more sensitive to metrical changes than nonmusicians, regardless of metrical complexity, but sensitivity to complex meter required sufficient exposure to musical genres featuring such meters.

Pearce hypothesizes that our musical enculturation depends on two cognitive processes: (1) statistical learning, in which listeners acquire internal cognitive models of statistical regularities present in the music to which they are exposed which is mostly from their culture; and (2) probabilistic prediction based on these learned models that enables listeners to organize and process their mental representations of music [9].

1.2 Music Cognition

Music encompasses non-conceptual Aesthetic cognition which is objective in nature. This understanding depends on the person's subjective character, mood and state of the mind. Our brains, bodies, and environment participate dynamically in driving cognitive processes [10]. Bodies interact with the environment to make sense of the world without involving complex intellectual processes [11]. There have been studies showing direct correlation between motor knowledge and auditory experience, in particular after long-term motor training, as with adult professional musicians [12]. It was found out that in infants and children, as well as in musical experts via a mimetic process, maturation and musical experience result in entrainment that allows for precision and flexibility in timing, a sense of participation and emotional communion, and a musical aesthetic that reveals the complexity and richness of human interaction.

The listener's or performer's ability to understand, perceive, and learn music is primarily a form of sensorimotor activity that depends on the level of musically related

motor knowledge of the agents in their continuous and dynamical coupling with the environment [13]. It was examined whether expectancy violations in musical harmonic sequences are also perceived as violations of the movement sequences necessary to produce them. For this, pianists imitated silent videos showing one hand playing chord sequences on a muted keyboard. From the results, it was suggested that the harmonic rules implied by observed actions induce expectations that influence action execution, and the magnitude of these effects of context and goal prioritization increases with musical training. Thus, musical training may lead to a domain-general representation of musical grammar, i.e., to a grammar of action.

Auditory-motor learning influences performer's memory for music [14]. Skilled pianists learned novel melodies in four conditions: auditory-only (listening), motor only (performing without sound), strongly coupled auditory-motor (normal performance), and weakly coupled auditory-motor (performing along with auditory recordings). From the results it was suggested that motor learning can aid performer's auditory recognition of music beyond auditory learning alone, and that motor learning is influenced by individual abilities in mental imagery and by variation in acoustic features.

It has been demonstrated that not only auditory and sensorimotor representations for music are connected, but musical representations in auditory cortex change more when the sensorimotor system is involved in training compared with when only the auditory system is involved in training [15]. Two groups of nonmusicians were musically trained over the course of 2 weeks. One group [sensorimotor-auditory (SA)] learned to play a musical sequence on the piano, whereas the other group [auditory (A)] listened to and made judgments about the music that had been played by participants of the sensorimotor-auditory group. Training-induced cortical plasticity was assessed by recording the musically elicited mismatch negativity (MMNm) from magnetoencephalographic measurements before and after training. SA and A groups showed significantly different cortical responses after training. Specifically, the SA group showed significant enlargement of MMNm after training compared with the A group, reflecting greater enhancement of musical representations in auditory cortex after sensorimotor-auditory training compared with after mere auditory training.

Mimetic comprehension as Mimetic motor action and Mimetic motor imagery is a part of human cognition generally and plays an important role in the development of music understanding and comprehension [16]. The conceptualization takes place not just in the form of sounds but also the listeners actions, where they act as co performers and processing the sounds as imageries generated in mind. Imagery may therefore enable musicians to generate the experience of sound or motor information that is altered or absent during encoding [14]. Adult's experience of movement while listening to music has comparable consequences for meter perception [17]. They were trained, while listening to an ambiguous rhythm with no accented beats, to bounce by bending their knees to interpret the rhythm either as a march or as a waltz. At test, adults identified as similar an auditory version of the rhythm pattern with accented strong beats that matched their previous bouncing experience in comparison with a version whose accents did not match. Thus, movement-sound interaction is fundamental to music processing throughout life.

1.3 Indian Hindustani Music Rhythm

In Indian classical music "Tala" refers to musical meter, that is any rhythmic beat or strike that measures musical time. The measure is typically established by hand clapping, waving, touching fingers on thigh or the other hand, verbally, striking of small cymbals, or a percussion instrument in the Indian subcontinent traditions. Talas have a vocalised and therefore recordable form wherein individual beats are expressed as phonetic representations of various strokes played upon the "Tabla"(Indian Percussion Instrument) (Figure 1).

Bol	Sound
Ti or Te	A dry, slapping sound played in the black circle (syahi) of the dayan.
Na or Ta	A resonant tone played on the outer ring (keenar) of the dayan.
Tin	A resonant tone played on the middle ring (sur) of the dayan.
Ga	A resonant tone played on the middle ring (sur) of the bayan.
Ka	A dry slap played on the bayan.
Dhin	Ga and Tin played at the same time.
Dha	Ga and Na/Ta played at the same time.
Tirikita	Ti, Ti, Ka, and Ti played quickly in a row

<p>Tin Tin Na O 2 3 Dhi Na 4 5 Dhi Na 6 7</p> <p>Rupaktaal</p>	<p>Dha Dhin Dhin Dha X 2 3 4 Dha Dhin Dhin Dha 5 6 7 8 Dha Tin Tin Ta O 10 11 12 Ta Dhin Dhin Dha 13 14 15 16</p> <p>Teental</p>	<p>Ka Dhi Te Dhi Te X 1 2 3 4 Dha -- 5 6 Ga Ti Te 7 8 9 Ti Te Ka/2 10 11 1/2</p> <p>Dharamital</p>
--	--	--

Bol and Tal

Figure 1 | Tala beat structure [18]

Along with raga which forms the fabric of a melodic structure, the tala forms the life cycle and thereby constitutes one of the two foundational elements of Indian music [19]. The first beat of any rhythmic cycle is called the “Sam” [20] (meaning even or equal), is always the most important and heavily emphasised. It is the point of resolution in the rhythm where the percussionist's and soloist's phrases culminate. In the North Indian system, the most common tala is “Teental” (Figure 2). It has sixteen (16) beats in four equal divisions (4+4+4+4). Every “Tal” has its own method of counting by using hand gestures. For example, to count the “Teental”, the subject has to clap on the first beat, clap on the 5th beat, then wave on the 9th beat and lastly again clap on the 13th beat.

Name	Beats	Division
Tintal (or Trital or Teental)	16	4+4+4+4
Jhoomra	14	3+4+3+4
Tilwada	16	4+4+4+4
Dhamar	14	5+2+3+4
Ektal and Chautal	12	2+2+2+2+2+2
Jhaptal	10	2+3+2+3
Keherwa	8	4+4
Rupak (Mughlai/Roopak)	7	3+2+2
Dadra	6	3+3

Figure 2| Talas in Indian Hindustani Music [18]

1.4 Music Education

In Music Education the main goal is to train people in different musical abilities [21], which could be grouped into the ones needed to become a musician, which we may call musicianship, and the ones for being able to appreciate music, which we may call listenership [22]. During the 20th century, many music education approaches were proposed and put into practice for the teaching of musicianship. For example DeVries [23] has shown that the Kodály method improves intonation, rhythm skills, music literacy, and the ability to sing in increasingly complex parts. However, not much has been proposed specifically for educating listenership independently of musicianship, besides encouraging active listening to music and therefore promoting implicit learning [24].

Active listening involves discerning of sounds, musical patterns, and their interrelations, together with providing meaning by connecting a particular auditory experience with other experiences and contextual cultural realities . Active listening to music has a great potential to develop critical skills, individual growth, and social transformation [25], but the challenge is how to educate it. The research coming from psychology on what is called perceptual learning [26] is very relevant here. It is based on the idea that one way in which perception becomes adapted to tasks and environments is by increasing the attention paid to perceptual dimensions and features that are important, and/or by decreasing attention to irrelevant dimensions and features. Processes of learning serve to optimize performance of particular tasks by discovering which information is relevant to them, refining and attuning perceptual mechanisms to selectively extract this information. By narrowing the focus of this understanding to pre subjective internalization of objective content, music education can reduce range and scope of subjective response and promote appropriate form of listening, oriented towards understanding musical object at the expense of subjectivity [27].

However, recent research and advances in music cognition hint that the best way to improve some important aspects of listenership, like memory for melodies or detecting out of tune notes, is to use sensory-motor-auditory training rather than just auditory training [11,12,13,14,15,16,17].

We have used these approaches to develop a cognitive experiment with perceptually relevant music excerpts of Indian Hindustani Music for Listenership Training.

1.5 Aims of the present work

The aim of this work is to study and test the hypothesis that music motor learning technique through mimetic comprehension could help to improve participants listenership ability and their appreciation for a culturally different music which they are not familiar with. For this, we chose to train participants (with less or no prior experience with Hindustani Music) on Indian Hindustani Music Rhythm and then analyse their listenership. They were trained on three different rhythms among two

sessions. For the training and practice parts of the sessions, we used a visual feedback tool which uses annotated music excerpts and shows the rhythm pattern divided into beats, with a cursor moving along with the music.

Participants were divided into two groups: Experimental Group (EG) and Control Group (CG). Both of them had access to training, practice materials and introductory videos during the experiment, but in addition, for the training process of the experimental group, we video-recorded the hands of a professional hindustani player performing the associated hand gestures for the target Tal being learned along with the visual feedback and asked them to imitate the hand gestures following the beat and the tempo of the Tal.

We hypothesized that participants in the EG will develop better listening and music comprehending abilities in perceiving rhythm of Hindustani musical excerpts thanks to the aid of mimetic comprehension than CG participants who were trained without it. For this, we evaluated the participants for (1) Detecting the “Sam” for various talas in 6 different audio excerpts and (2) Recognising the different “Talas” among 12 audio excerpts.

Chapter 2

Materials and Methods

2.1 Participants

Four subjects, 3 male and 1 female of average age 25 participated in the training. The study was carried out in the masters room located in the Information and Communication Technologies Engineering (ETIC) department of the Universitat Pompeu Fabra, Barcelona. The participants were divided into two groups : three subjects for experimental (EG) and one for the control group (CG). Participants for EG on an average listened to music more than 10 hours weekly, with more than 4 years of experience as a musician and a willingness of 4.33 on a scale of 5 to take the training. Participant for CG listened to music for 0-5 hours weekly, with more than 5 years of experience as a musician and a willingness of 4 on a scale of 5 to take the training. They belonged to various nationalities other than Indian, having no prior exposure to Indian Hindustani Music.

2.2 Materials

The interface for the whole experiment has been developed on a webpage using p5.js (Java Script Library). The entire repository for the training experiment is available for public use on Github for its reusability and reproducibility [31].

Participants were asked to take the Modular PROMS test [28]. This test is available online. The PROMS is a novel musical test battery that measures perceptual musical skills objectively across multiple modalities, such as timbre, tuning, melody, pitch, rhythm, and tempo. We asked participants to customize the test by just choosing “Accent” subtest. This was to get an idea about the participant’s musical perception ability regarding rhythm. For listening to audio during the experiment, participants used good quality headphones with optimal volume level. Participants details such as name

age, ethnicity, musicianship, instrument playing experience etc were taken using Google forms [29].

Figure 3 | Screenshot of the Modular PROMS test

The introductory video was taken from the “North Indian Classical Music I: Fundamental Elements” course on Kadenze platform [30]. The video introduces the participant to philosophy of Hindustani Music and the concept of “Laya” which is basically a pattern repeating itself over time and the formation of “Tal” (beat pattern) from “Laya”.

Listenership Training Setup for Hindustani Classical Music Rhythm

This page contains a series of rhythm training exercises for aiding the understanding and appreciation of Hindustani classical music rhythm. Their purpose is to help in the development of the listenership skills for perceiving the main rhythmic structures, which in Indian tradition is formulated as **The Tāl**.

These exercises complement the listening experience with the visualization of key aspects of the rhythmic structures, as well as allow certain interaction with them.

Please go through the following steps to start the training.

Note: It is advised to use good quality headphones at optimal loudness level.

Take the Musical Ability Test

Please select the following Subtests and take the test by pressing on the link:

Note: After taking the test, save the results on Dekstop in form of **PDF** by your name.

1) Accent

Fill your Details

Please fill the form and enter your details.

First Training Session

This Session involves series of introductinal, training and practice exercises for Hindustani Rhythm. These exercises are followed by a short listenership ability test.

Second Training Session

This session covers more complex rhythmic patterns. Also, this session would be followed by a short test.

Figure 4| Screenshot of the Training Interface

Training videos for beat structure representation were screen-recorded by using tool for visual rhythm feedback from Hindustani Tools available on Dunya website [31] using QuickTime player [32]. Training videos for experimental group were recorded with hand gestures of beats using a DSLR camera and edited using Final Cut Pro software [33]. These videos contain the visual feedback tool and hand gestures, while training videos for control group contains only the visual feedback tool. The tool shows the beat divisions with a moving cursor (red dot on circle) following the rhythm of the song (Figure 5).

Figure 5| Screenshot of training video for control group

Figure 6| Screenshot of training video for experimental group

The training videos contained excerpts of Hindustani Classical Music. They showed the beat structure of the rhythm with moving cursor along the rhythm of music for CG (Figure 5), but for EG it also had video of beat counting using hand gestures for mimetic motor comprehension (Figure 6).

Session	Taal (Beat Pattern)	Duration of videos	Song used, Artist	Duration of excerpt
1	Tintal (16 beats)	11m	Solo Tabla recording	2 mins
			Raag Yaman, Omkar Dadarkar	2:00-5:00
			Raag Malkauns, Satyasheel Deshpande	29:55-32:55
			Raag Gavti, Sandip Ghosh	22:00-24:00
2	Ektal (12 beats)	8 m	Solo Tabla recording	2 mins
			Raag Bhairav, Kumar Gandharva	18:05-19:35
			Raag Ahir Bhairon, Omkar Dadarkar	32:40-34:10
2	Jhaptal (10 beats)	11min	Solo Tabla recording	2 mins
			Raag Malkauns, Satyasheel Deshpande	23:00-26:00
			Raag Bhimpalasi, Omkar Dadarkar	4:30-7:30
			Raag Shree, Kaustuv Kumar Ganguli	50:00-53:00

Table 1| Data for rhythm training for CG and EG

The annotated music audio dataset used in the visual feedback and training tool on Dunya has been taken from Saraga dataset under Creative Commons License [34]. This repository contains time aligned melody, rhythm and structural annotations for two large open corpora of Indian Art Music (Indian Carnatic and Hindustani music). It also contains “Sam” annotations referring to rhythmic cycle boundaries stored as timestamps which is necessary for our training evaluation.

For the first session, participants were trained for “Tintal”. Out of the training videos for experimental group, 1 video consisted of only solo beat recording on Tabla (Indian Percussion Instrument) accompanied by visual feedback taken from Tal visualizer tool and mimetic comprehension using hand gestures, while the other 3 video excerpts were taken from the Tal visualizer tool on having visual feedback and mimetic comprehension, these songs are real excerpts of Classical Hindustani Music.

The screenshot displays a practice tool for "Raag Gavti" by Sandip Ghosh. At the top, it shows performance statistics: Attempts (0), Hits (0), and Points (0). The main area features a central diagram of a hand with various stroke labels (DHA, dhin, ta, tin, dha) and a timeline at the bottom. The timeline is divided into "rūpak tāl" and "tintal" sections. The top bar displays "Raag Gavti -" and performance metrics: Attempts (0), Hits (0), and Points (0). The main area features a central diagram of a hand with various stroke labels (DHA, dhin, ta, tin, dha) and a timeline at the bottom. The timeline is divided into "rūpak tāl" and "tintal" sections. The top bar displays "Raag Gavti -" and performance metrics: Attempts (0), Hits (0), and Points (0). The main area features a central diagram of a hand with various stroke labels (DHA, dhin, ta, tin, dha) and a timeline at the bottom. The timeline is divided into "rūpak tāl" and "tintal" sections.

Figure 7| Screenshot of practice tool for “Sam” training

For the control group, the videos comprised only of the visual rhythm tool without hand gestures. In the same session, for practice participants used the “Sam” practice tool (Figure 7) using for the listed audio excerpts. This tool shows the visual feedback of beat structure with the scoreboard showing the score for hitting sam correctly. The test for the first session was conducted using the same tool as used for practice (Figure 7) [35].

Session	Category	Taal (Beat Pattern)	Song Used, Artist Name	Duration of excerpt
1	Practice	Tintal (16 beats)	1) Raag Bhimpalasi, Satyasheel Deshpande	22:00-24:00
			2) Raag Gavti, Sandip Ghosh	23:00-25:00
2	Practice	Ektal (12 beats)	1) Raag Bhairav, Kumar Gandharva	19:00-21:00
			2) Raag Ahir Bhairon, Omkar Dadarkar	33:00-35:00
2	Practice	Jhaptal (10 beats)	1) Raag Malkauns, Satyasheel Deshpande	7:00-9:00
			2) Raag Bhimpalasi, Omkar Dadarkar	10:00-12:00

Table 2| Data for rhythm practice for EG and CG

For the second session, the participants were trained for “Ektal” and “Jhaptal” beat patterns. Out of the training videos of Ektal for experimental group, 1 video consists of only solo beat recording on Tabla (Indian Percussion Instrument) accompanied by

visual feedback and mimetic comprehension, while the other 2 video excerpts were taken from Hindustani songs. These videos also have visual feedback along with mimetic comprehension using hand gestures. For control group videos only comprise of visual rhythm tool without any hand gestures.

For training videos of Jhaptal also, 1 video consists of only solo beat recording on Tabla (Indian Percussion Instrument) accompanied by visual feedback and hand gestures, while other 3 video excerpts were taken from “Tal” visualizer tool with different audio excerpts. These videos also have visual feedback along with mimetic comprehension. For control group videos comprised of only visual feedback tool without any mimetic comprehension.

For the practice participants were asked to use the “Sam” practice tool for listed excerpts from Saraga having “Ektal” and “Jhaptal” rhythms (Figure 7). This tool showed the visual feedback of beat structure with the scoreboard showing the score for hitting sam correctly (Figure 7) [36].

Later, for “Tal” identification and qualitative analysis, a google form was created with 12 multiple choice questions for “Tal” identification with different Indian Hindustani Music audio excerpts and 9 questions for qualitative feedback of the training [37]. The parameters for qualitative feedback were focused on determining subject’s behavioral condition during the course of training.

Session	Type of Test	Tal	Materials	Duration
1	“Sam” Detection	Tintal (16 beats)	1) Raag Bhimpalasi, Satyasheel Deshpande	22:00-24:00
			2) Raag Gavti, Sandip Ghosh	23:00-25:00
2	“Sam” Detection	Ektal (12 beats)	1) Raag Bhairav, Kumar Gandharva	19:00-21:00
			2) Raag Ahir Bhairon, Omkar Dadarkar	33:00-35:00
	“Sam” Detection	Jhaptal (10 beats)	1) Raag Malkauns, Satyasheel Deshpande	7:00-9:00
			2) Raag Bhimpalasi, Omkar Dadarkar	10:00-12:00
	“Tal” Detection	-	3 audio (Only solo Beat Pattern on Tabla)	1.5min
			9 audio (Randomly chosen Excerpts from Hindustani music corpora)	4.5min

Table 3| Data for the rhythm “Tal” identification test and “Sam” detection

2.3 Methods

The whole experiment for a participant takes approximately 2 hours to complete. In order to make the training comfortable, it was divided into two sessions of approximately 1 hour each with a small break. Participants were asked to wear good quality headphones at optimal volume level and follow the steps as shown in the interface.

2.3.1 First Session

Participants were asked to take the Modular PROMS [28] (Figure 3) test only with “Accent” subtest and then fill their details on an online Google form [29].

After, both groups of participants were shown the same introductory video about Hindustani Music rhythm. Then, the experimental group was shown videos for training of Tintal with mimetic comprehension using hand gestures (Figure 6). To count the beat participants of the experimental group were asked to mimic the hand gestures following the video by clapping on the first beat, clapping on the 5th beat, then waving on the 9th beat and lastly again clapping on the 13th beat.

However, the control group was shown only visual feedback of the beat structure without any mimetic comprehension (Figure 5). They were asked to analyze the beat and focus their attention on “Sam” (Start of new beat cycle).

Figure 8| Methodology for the training experiment

After the training, participants of both control and experimental group practiced the tital rhythm “Sam” detection using the visual feedback tool (Figure 7). The participants belonging to the experimental group were asked to practice the “Sam” detection using aid of the mimetic comprehension using hand gestures as practiced before in the training videos along with visual feedback and audio.

However, the participants in the control group were asked to practice “Sam” identification by using only visual feedback with audio. They were allowed to take eight minutes for practice and then notify when they were ready to take the test.

After, participants of both groups took the “Sam detection” test using the same tool. They were shown the cursor moving along with the rhythm of the song for the starting thirty seconds and then they were asked to press the key “s” on the keyboard while listening to the audio excerpt for the correct “Sam” without the cursor. The number of attempts and correctly hit “Sam” were recorded.

2.3.2 Second Session

In the second training session for training on Ektal and Jhaptal beats. Participants for experimental group were shown the training videos with visual feedback and hand gestures (Figure 6). They were asked to count the beat by clapping on the appropriate beat, which in 1) Jhaptal is beats 1, 3 and 8 and wave of the hand at beat 6. 2) Ektal is beats 1, 5, 9, 11 and a wave of the hand at beat 3 and 7. However, again the control group was shown only visual feedback of the beat structure without any mimetic comprehension (Figure 5). They were asked to analyze the beat pattern and focus their attention on “Sam”.

After the training, participants of both control and experimental group practiced the “Sam” detection for Ektal and Jhaptal rhythms using the practice tool (Figure 7). The participants belonging to the experimental group were asked to practice the “Sam” detection using aid of the hand gestures as trained before. However, the participants in the control group were asked to practice “Sam” by using the aid of visual feedback

with audio. They were allowed to take eight minutes for practice and then notify when they were ready to take the test.

Please listen to the following audio excerpts and choose the correct option:

Section 1

This section consists of three audio excerpts containing Ektal, Jhaptal and Tintal. Please select the correct option for the following song excerpts.

1) <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1D6G1iLW27Sle1PBUjLGLvnZIAfkuQE0Q/view?usp=sharing> 1 point

Tintal (16 Beats)

Jhaptal (10 Beats)

Ektal (12 Beats)

Figure 9| Screenshot of test

After the training, the participants of both the groups were asked to go through a series of test exercises in which: 1) They were shown the Cursor moving along with the rhythm of the song in the starting 30 seconds and then they were asked to press the key “s” on the keyboard while listening to the audio excerpt for the correct “Sam”. The number of attempts and correctly hit “Sam” were recorded. 2) They had to identify the “Tal” (beat pattern) present in the 12 given excerpts, by listening to them analytically

and choosing the right answer in multiple choice questions. At last, they had to answer 9 questions for the qualitative feedback.

Chapter 3

Evaluation and Results

3.1 Modular PROMS

Participants for the EG scored an average of 72 percent of maximum points whereas the participant of CG scored 81 percent. Results of the participant of the CG (81%) were very close to those of the best participant of the EG group (83%) which may allow for accurate comparisons between them.

Figure 10| Modular PROMS Test Scores

3.2 “Sam” Detection

The participants correct “Sam” detection and accuracy scores have been represented in the graphs below. Here the correct “Sam” detection scores indicates the number of correct “Sam” detected divided by the total number of “Sams” present in the excerpt and “Accuracy” scores indicate total number of correct “Sams” detected divided by the total number of attempts (number of times the key “s” is pressed on the keyboard).

Figure 11| Subject 1 “Sam” detection score

Subject 1’s correct “Sam” detection percentage increased from 38.5 for Tintal, 67 for Ektal and 92.5 for Jhaptal and overall average of 66. However, the accuracy had an overall average percentage of 48.2.

Figure 12| Subject 2 "Sam" detection score

Subject 2's correct "Sam" detection percentage was 94.7 for Tintal, 81.5 for Ektal and 100 for Jhaptal and average of 92.1. The accuracy had an overall average percentage of 92.8.

Figure 13| Subject 3 "Sam" detection score

Subject 3's correct "Sam" detection percentage increased from 92.1 for Tintal, 95 for Ektal and 100 for Jhaptal and average of 95.7. The accuracy had an overall average percentage of 92.9.

Figure 14| Subject 4 "Sam" detection score

Subject 4's correct "Sam" detection percentage was 100 for Tintal, 92.5 for Ektal and 100 for Jhaptal and average of 97.5. The accuracy had an overall average percentage of 99.

The average percentage for correct "Sam" detection for EG was 85.2 while for CG it was 92.1. The accuracy average for CG was 92.9 and for EG 80.

3.3 “Tal” Recognition

For the task of recognizing the rhythm pattern present in the audio excerpts, the participants of EG showed higher performance with an average score percentage of 86, while for the CG it was 67.

Figure 15| “Tal” recognition result

Correlation and T-test scores

Pearson’s correlations were performed between Modular PROMS test scores, “Sam” detection scores, “Accuracy” scores and “Tal” recognition scores. The R^2 and p-values were found out to be (0.067,0.73), (0.09,0.68) and (0.09,0.68) respectively. Also, a two sample t-test was performed for “Sam” detection, “Accuracy” and “Tal” recognition scores for which the p-values came out to be 0.64, 0.61 and 0.32 respectively.

3.4 Qualitative Analysis

The results show that the participants of both EG and CG were highly involved (Average: 9.5/10) in the training session with low stress levels (Average: 3/10). They found out the pace of training to be slow but moderately demanding (Average: 7.75/10). They showed high learning levels from the training (Average: 8.25/10).

Figure 16| Qualitative Analysis 1

Figure 17| Qualitative Analysis 2

All subjects found the interface useful. They all agreed that they would be able to detect the rhythm, if they heard Hindustani Music later in future. However, only half of the participants were satisfied with the training.

Chapter 4

Discussion

We used Indian Hindustani music excerpts with visual feedback of the rhythm component and mimetic comprehension using hand gestures to investigate listenership training for differently encultured participants. We selected specific music excerpts out of the available music corpora having perceptually relevant rhythmic parts for the audio. Participants demonstrated high learning and sensitivity with very high involvement during the period of training, both for experimental and control group.

We found that participants were successfully trained to analyse and recognise Hindustani Music rhythm. For all the participants the “Sam Detection scores” were the highest for the last rhythm “Jhaptal”. The performance also increased from the start of the training to the end. Overall, the participants of EG and CG had an average percentage for correct “Sam” detection as 85.2 and 92.1 and accuracy average 92.9 and 80. Participant from the CG did not perform worse than the rest of participants which may imply that mimetic comprehension did not play a role in improving the rhythmic perception participants needed to detect the sam

We also found no significant or apparent correlation between the results of the PROMS test which measured some of their rhythmic perceptual abilities with their “Sam Detection Scores” or with their results in production abilities. Subject2 and Subject4 from the EG performed similar to Subject3 from the CG although Subject4 scores in the PROMS test were the lowest. This may be an indication that we may need to include more rhythm sub-tests from the PROMS test like: Rhythm, Rhythm-to-Melody, Accent, or Tempo in order to interpret better the results of our participants based on their rhythm perception skills before the experiment (which will inevitably extend the duration of the experiment) or that perceptual skills on rhythm don’t predict rhythmic abilities in production.

Interestingly, we found in the qualitative results that Subject1 from the EG group who scored the lowest score reported higher levels of stress during the training. Warning us about the importance of maintaining this parameter in order to take it into account for future extensions of this experiment.

From the qualitative results of the participants, the training setup turned out to be useful in involving participants with different cultural backgrounds to develop listenership abilities for Indian Hindustani Music. During the course of training participants had high involvement. They found out the “Sam” detection and “Tal” recognition tests to be competitive and interesting tasks. They were keen on knowing their ability to detect and measure their performance. Their learning scores from the analysis were high which shows that we were successful in improving their rhythm comprehending ability.

Also, from the Tal recognition scores we found out that CG had the lowest performance than the EG. Since, there was no significant correlation (from t-test) between modular prompts score, and Tal recognition scores, it is possible that mimetic comprehension enables the participant of EG to comprehend and label the beat structure more accurately than the participant of CG. If that trend continues in the future with more participants to compare, we could relate it with recent work that shows how auditory-motor learning improves auditory memory for melodies in music [12]. This could mean that the beneficial effects of auditory-motor learning in auditory memory are not only confined to the memory of melodies but also to the memory of rhythmic structures which would help to create and develop a bigger framework of abstraction as the task of recognising Talas by memory may require.

This setup instead of being a cognitive listenership training setup could be incorporated in Music Education to promote the music appreciation and listenership ability in general. Perhaps future work can give us a better picture about the feasibility and applicability of the training.

Chapter 5

Future work

From the research done during this thesis, it can be said that the training model is successful in improving people's listenership ability regarding Indian Hindustani Music focusing its rhythm aspects. However, several aspects can be improved in a future work.

In the current work due to several restrictions and limited participation, we could gather data for only a small group of participants. However, training with bigger and more diverse participants with less musical background could provide more accurate data in support of our current methodology. The training instead of being taken in single sitting can be divided into duration of one week which could also help us understand the learning regarding long term memory of the participants.

The training setup we have developed has high potential to be converted into a music appreciation and listenership teaching setup. Training methods used online promote instrument learning rather than music listenership and appreciation. Also, most of the resources available online has content based on Western Music, there are very few sources for different culture Art music like Indian Classical Music etc. We are in need of developing an easily accessible, public music teaching setup which focuses on listenership, understanding, appreciation and learning. It can be made available online and used by a vast amount of people of all ages around the globe. It would also enable us to gather more data of the users with which we can add to this research. It can be used to get feedback from the users which can help us improve our setup further. Also, this current methodology could be incorporated for listenership training for music belonging to different cultures. Through our training experiment, we feel motivated to develop such setup and promote formation of future community of people, who will be connected musically.

Furthermore, the training could be made more engaging by the incorporation of other feedback mechanisms like haptic feedback for the rhythm along with other feedback systems. The visual feedback could be enhanced by integrating the training videos with live video instrument recordings, enabling the user to establish the perceptual relation between music rhythm patterns with instrument playing body gestures. There is yet an ample amount of research to be done to understand the role of such cognitive feedback systems on music learning. We plan to follow this path.

Chapter 6

Conclusions

We used Indian Hindustani music excerpts with visual feedback of the rhythm component and mimetic comprehension using hand gestures to investigate listenership training for differently encultured participants. We selected specific music excerpts out of the available music corpora having perceptually relevant rhythmic parts for the audio. To carry out experiments, we gathered data from 4 participants out of which 3 were in Experimental group and 1 in the control group. The participants had no prior experience with Hindustani Music. We asked participants of EG to use hand gestures to promote mimetic comprehension.

From the results we found out that participants demonstrated high learning and sensitivity with very high involvement during the period of training, both for experimental and control group. But, because of very small sample size we were not able to prove the correlation between the use of music motor learning techniques through mimetic comprehension and participants listenership ability. But, considering the performance of subjects and their feedback, we can say that the training was successful in developing listenership and appreciation ability for Indian Hindustani Music.

Currently active listening is the most common method to develop listenership for music. We know that for learning the interaction takes place between the organism and the environment. So, even while listening to music our whole body interacts with the surroundings. Not only our sensorimotor and auditory systems connected, but also sensorimotor-auditory training causes plastic reorganizational changes in the auditory cortex over and above changes introduced by auditory training alone [15]. So, interacting with music involving sensori-motor techniques might accelerate the development of listenership ability in general.

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Appendix A

Reproducibility

The repository containing the source code to run the training setup is made available on GitHub. The repository also contains a readme file with all the information required to run the setup.

<https://github.com/rachit29/Hindustani-Listenership-Training-Setup>

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